

alcohols (ethanol and methanol), and other molecules. On the other hand ICP-OES allowed the quantification of 14 elements and five inorganic anions. Xylem sap analysis will lead to a better understanding of the biology and complex nutritional requirements of olive xylem-inhabiting microorganisms, including *Xylella fastidiosa*, and to help designing artificial growing media to improve culturing of the olive microbiome. Study supported by Projects 727987 XF-ACTORS (EU-H2020) & AGL2016-75606-R (MEIC Spain and FEDER-EU)

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2.7 *X. fastidiosa* associated with extensive mortality of almond trees in Mallorca

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Abstract: In 2008 a new disease causing mortality of almond trees appeared in orchards located in Son Carrió, east of Mallorca. Disease symptoms were described 'as rapid collapse of branches during mid-summer, chlorosis of leaves, which suddenly wilted, as well as bud and shoot'. In the following two summers the disease had spread at a rate of mortality never seen before in Majorca, and five years later thousands of almond trees had died throughout the island. Eventually, the disease was associated with a complex of pathogenic fungi of the genera *Phaeoamoniella*, *Phaeocremonium* and *Botryosphaeria*, although the causal agent was not determined (Gramaje *et al.* 2012).

In October 2016, *X. fastidiosa* was officially detected in a Garden Centre in Porto Cristo, 1.5 kms from the first focus of the almond disease. Multilocus-sequence typing of three isolates from infected *Prunus avium* identified them as *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa*, ST1, the same genotype group causing Almond leaf scorch disease (ALSD) in California. To date 46 positives from Almond have been reported.

Here we will show the parallelism of the outbreak of the Olive Quick Decline Syndrome caused by *X. fastidiosa* in Apulia, Italy, with that of the ALS in Majorca. We will provide evidence reviewing the etiology; the epidemiology; the genotypes of the pathogen associated with symptomatic almond trees, and we will present the results of ongoing research to revisit what might have been the first outbreak of *X. fastidiosa* in Europe.

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2.8 Pathogenicity of some fungal species associated with olive quick decline syndrome

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Abstract: Several fungal species have been found associated with the Olive Quick Decline Syndrome (OQDS) caused by *X. fastidiosa* CoDiRO strain, among which some have long been recognized as primary pathogens of many plants (i.e. *Phaeocremonium* and *Pleurostomophora* spp.), whereas other have not been described before. The new species *Ps. oleae* and *Ps. oleicola*, were associated with brown wood streaking of various olive varieties, both on young and centenarian trees. In order to ascertain the role of these fungi in the OQDS, pathogenicity tests were performed both in glasshouse, on young plants, and in the open field, on centenarian olive plants cv Cellina di Nardò. In glasshouse

tests, fungal strains (*Ph. aleophilum* B1a, *Ph. rubrigenum* N20, *Ps. oleae* Fv84, *Ps. oleicola* M24, *Pseudophaeomoniella* sp. M51), were inoculated alone or in combination with *X. fastidiosa* CoDiRO strain. For the test in the field, naturally *X. fastidiosa* CoDiRO-infected and uninfected centenarian plants were inoculated with the same fungal strains. Results from the glasshouse tests, collected two years after the inoculation, indicate that fungal strain(s) alone are able to colonize the olive xylem, and to cause wood streaking. However, only few twigs showed wilting symptoms. Conversely, the combined inoculations with *X. fastidiosa* CoDiRO, induced extensive OQDS wilting symptoms. To date, results from the field observation 8 months after fungal inoculation show no differences in symptoms severity between *X. fastidiosa* infected and healthy plants.

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2.9 Role of argininosuccinate synthase in Pierce's Disease development in grapevines

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Abstract: Pierce's disease (PD) in grapevines is among several deadly plant diseases caused by strains of *X. fastidiosa*. The analysis of the secretome of wild type *X. fastidiosa* Temecula1 (WT) revealed LesA (lipase/esterase) and PrtA (protease) as the most abundant secreted proteins involved in virulence, cell growth, motility, and biofilm formation. Enzymatic activity of LesA has also been shown to be closely associated with PD symptoms. *X. fastidiosa* mutants deficient in prtA display an obligate planktonic phenotype, secrete high levels of LesA, are hypervirulent and accumulate high levels of argininosuccinate synthase (ArgG). ArgG is an enzyme involved in arginine biosynthesis and was previously characterized as virulence factor in the rice pathogen *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv *oryzae*. High levels of arginine in infected leaves of citrus was also associated with citrus variegated chlorosis caused by *X. fastidiosa*. Therefore, we aim to investigate if the arginine metabolism that appears to be closely associated with LesA activity contributes to *X. fastidiosa* growth and virulence. Thus, argG coding sequence in *X. fastidiosa* WT (PD0291) was disrupted and grapevines inoculated with *X. fastidiosa* argG⁻ mutant presented less symptomatic necrotic regions on the edges of the leaves compared with *X. fastidiosa* WT after 15-weeks inoculation. The relationship of arginine metabolism with PD symptom development and the expression of LesA will allow a better understanding of how arginine contributes to *X. fastidiosa* virulence in planktonic phase leading to disease development.

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